

Temperature Coefficients, Quantum Efficiency and the Relation between Intensity and Velocity of the Hydrolysis of Cane Sugar in Visible and Infra-red Radiations.

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A few years ago Lindemann (*Phil. Mag.*, 1920, *vi*, 40, 671) pointed out that on the basis of the simple radiation hypothesis, the inversion of cane sugar must be enormously accelerated by sunlight but he stated that the reaction actually proceeds at the same rate whether it is exposed to sunlight or not. In publications from these laboratories (Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, 119, 177; *Faraday Soc. Disc.*, 1921) it has been shown that the statement of Lindemann is not correct and that a solution of sucrose in tropical sunlight is completely inverted even in absence of acids on long exposure, whilst in presence of hydrochloric acid the inversion is distinctly accelerated by sunlight. In a subsequent communication, Banerji and Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 134, 172) investigated the kinetics of sucrose inversion in presence of hydrochloric acid in sunlight and showed that the temperature coefficient for a ten-degree rise of temperature can vary from 3.4 to 2.78 in sunlight according to the variations in light intensity, whilst the temperature coefficient of the dark reaction has a value 3.82 under the same conditions.

In this communication we are submitting the results obtained in the determination of temperature coefficients, quantum efficiency and the influence of variation of intensity on the hydrolysis of sucrose in light of different wave-lengths.

The experimental arrangement is the same as described in a previous paper (Bhattacharya and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 143).

The velocity of the hydrolysis of sucrose was determined by a polarimeter.

In order to determine the light absorption of cane sugar in different parts of the visible spectrum the extinction coefficients have been measured by a Nutting's spectrophotometer.

The following are the experimental results:—

Temperature = 30°. Region $\lambda = 4725\text{Å}$.

Time.	Reading on the polarimeter scale.	k_1 Monomolecular.
0 hours.	11.4	—
2	11.95	0.000146
4	10.50	0.000149
6	10.10	0.000146
	Mean	0.000147

20% Cane sugar (15 c.c.) and N/20-Hydrochloric Acid (5 c.c.).

Condition.	Temp.	k_1 Mono-molecular.	k_1 After deducting the dark reaction.	Temp. coefficient.	Temperature coefficient after deducting the dark reaction.	Quantum efficiency.
Dark.	30°	0.0000975	—	3.86	—	—
	35°	0.000189	—			
	45°	0.000727	—			
(5000-4450Å)	30°	0.000147	0.0000495	—	—	—
	35°	0.000278	0.000089			
	45°	0.00101	0.000283			
Mean 4725Å	35°	0.000278	0.000089	—	3.18	455
	45°	0.00101	0.000283			
(5350-5450Å)	30°	0.000125	0.0000275	—	—	250
	35°	0.000242	0.000053			
	45°	0.000903	0.000176			
Mean 5650Å	35°	0.000242	0.000053	—	3.32	385
	45°	0.000903	0.000176			
(7608-7000Å)	30°	0.0001096	0.0000121	—	—	145
	35°	0.000212	0.000023			
	45°	0.000812	0.000085			
Mean 7304Å	35°	0.000212	0.000023	—	3.70	162
	45°	0.000812	0.000085			
1000 Watt lamp	35°	0.000548	0.000359	—	—	16.5×10^6
„ 10% Cane sugar	35°	0.000794	0.000522	—	—	20×10^6

Light absorption.

$$\text{Extinction coefficient} = \frac{\text{Density reading on the scale}}{\text{Thickness of the cell.}}$$

Region in A. U.	7000	6500	5970	5600	5000	4800	4720	4550	4400
Extinction coefficient.	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.14

From the results recorded in the foregoing pages it will be observed that Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence is not at all applicable. The quantum efficiency increases with the temperature and concentration of the reacting system and the frequency of the incident radiation.

The experimental results show that in all cases the temperature coefficients of the photochemical changes are less than those of the corresponding thermal reactions. The greater the acceleration in light of different wave-lengths, the less the temperature coefficient.

It is believed that the photochemical reactions are brought about mostly by violet and ultra-violet radiations. Our experimental results however, prove that the inversion of sucrose and other chemical changes can be accelerated by radiation of wave-length 7304\AA which lies in the infra-red region (cf. Bhattacharya and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 451). We have carefully measured the extinction coefficient of the reacting system by Nutting's spectrophotometer and have found appreciable absorption in the region 7000\AA . It is apparent, therefore, that the reacting substances actually absorb the radiation wave-length of 7304\AA and are activated by the absorption of energy and then react chemically. We have also observed that the hydrolysis of sucrose can be accelerated by radiations of wave-lengths 5650\AA and 4725\AA and these wave-lengths are also appreciably absorbed by the reacting system.

According to the radiation hypothesis of Trautz (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1906, 4, 106), Perrin (*Ann. Physique*, 1919, 11, 1) and Lewis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 2330; 1915, 107, 233) we can easily calculate from the temperature coefficient of the thermal reaction, the wave-length of the radiation which should accelerate the chemical change. The following result has been obtained:—

	Temperature coeff. (dark.)	Wave-length.
Hydrolysis of cane sugar.	8.85	1.19μ

We are of the opinion that the wave-lengths obtained by calculation from the thermal temperature coefficients may be regarded as the threshold limit. No acceleration of the sucrose inversion is possible with radiations of wave-lengths longer than 11900\AA . Our experimental results show that sucrose inversion is appreciably accelerated by

radiations of $\lambda=7804\text{\AA}$. The main difference between our conception and the Perrin-Lewis radiation hypothesis is that according to the latter view the wave-length calculated from the temperature coefficient should bring about the maximum speed of that reaction in question whilst according to the conception now put forward, the threshold frequency is the minimum frequency necessary for the carrying out of the reaction.

The Relation between Intensity and Velocity of the Hydrolysis of Cane Sugar.

The experimental arrangement is the same as described in a previous paper (Bhattacharya and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 197).

The following are the experimental results:—

20% Cane sugar (15 c.c.) and N/20-HCl (5 c.c.)

Temperature = 35°.

Diameter of aperture.	Area of the aperture.	k_1 Monomolecular.	k_1 After deducting the dark reaction velocity $k_1(\text{dark})=0\cdot000189$.
A. Source 1000 watt lamp.			
2 cm.	3.14 sq. cm.	0.000548	0.000359 (I)
0.8	0.5024 ,,	0.000218	0.000059 (II)
B. Region $\lambda=5650\text{\AA}$ (from 1000 watt lamp).			
2	3.14 sq.	0.000228	0.000039 (I)
1	0.785 cm.	0.000195	0.00006 (II)

Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to the change in intensity.	If proportional to the square root of the change in intensity.
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A. Source 1000 watt lamp.

$$\frac{\text{I}}{\text{II}} = 6 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25 \qquad \sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$$

B. Region $\lambda=5650\text{\AA}$ (from 1000 watt lamp).

$$\frac{\text{I}}{\text{II}} = 6.5 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.785} = 4 \qquad \sqrt{4} = 2$$

In order to be sure that the light absorption varies proportionately with intensity of radiation, the following experiments were performed using a radiomicrometer.

Source.	Diameter of the aperture.	Absorption by the reacting system (deflection in cms.)
1000 watt-lamp.	2 cm.	0.3
	0.8	0.05

Ratio of intensity.

$$\frac{I}{I_1} = \frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$$

Ratio of absorption.

$$\frac{0.3}{0.05} = 6$$

Variation of Quantum Yield with the Variation of Intensity.

Source 1000 watt lamp.

Diameter of the aperture.	Quantum efficiency.
2 cm.	16.5×10^3
0.8	19.2×10^3

From the foregoing results it will be evident that the relation between intensity and velocity of the hydrolysis of cane sugar varies from 1 to $\frac{3}{2}$ depending upon the ratio of the thermal and photochemical reactions.

In a foregoing paper we have obtained similar results with several other photochemical reactions. These results show that by increasing the velocity of the dark reaction and exposing it to radiation which is slightly absorbed by the reacting system a truly photochemical reaction which is proportional to the square root of the incident radiation, becomes directly proportional to the intensity of the incident radiation.

On the other hand, a photochemical reaction which is proportional to the square of the incident radiation or is directly proportional can be made to be proportional to the square root of the incident radiation by decreasing the dark reaction velocity and increasing the photochemical velocity.

From the measurements of the absorption of incident radiation by a radiomicrometer we find that the light absorption is directly proportional to the intensity of the incident radiation.

Hence we venture to suggest that the velocity of sucrose inversion is likely to be proportional to $I^{\frac{1}{2}}$ or $I^{\frac{1}{3}}$ when illuminated with intense ultra-violet radiations and that the relation between intensity or absorption of the incident radiation and the velocity of a photochemical reaction can vary from any proper fraction to 2 depending upon the ratio of the thermal and photochemical reaction velocities.

We have also determined the quantum yield with the variation of intensity and hence the absorption and have found that the quantum yield increases with the decrease of intensity, i. e., the absorption.

Summary.

1. The temperature coefficients of the hydrolysis of cane sugar between 35° and 45° are 3.85 (dark), 3.18 ($\lambda = 4725 \text{ \AA}$), 3.32 ($\lambda = 5650 \text{ \AA}$) and 3.7 ($\lambda = 7304 \text{ \AA}$).

2. The quantum yield is very high and it increases with the temperature and the frequency of the incident radiation.

3. The extinction coefficient measurements show that there is appreciable absorption in the region $\lambda = 7000 \text{ \AA}$.

4. The absorption of light by an acid solution of sucrose varies proportionately with the intensity of the incident radiation. The same solution shows appreciable absorption of radiations of wavelengths from 4400 to 7000 \AA .

5. The relation between intensity or the absorption of light and the velocity of the hydrolysis of sucrose varies from 1 to $\frac{3}{2}$ depending upon the velocities of the thermal and photochemical reactions.

6. The quantum yield increases with the decrease in intensity or the absorption of the incident radiation.